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In the collection of materials of the conference, the role and role of Science, Education and production in the era of globalization, the pressing problems of the issues of interaction of these processes, feedback on their solutions were presented by mature specialists of the field.

In addition, research on the scientific and practical topic, carried out in the economics, Exact Sciences, Natural Sciences and socio-humanities during the globalization period, information is presented in the scientific and practical fields, which includes the latest innovative technologies in the fields of production.

It can be argued that this collection is one of the specific intersections of current thoughts and innovative ideas of the world of science. This scientific and practical conference was actively attended by professors and scientific researchers engaged in scientific research in Uzbekistan and foreign countries. In increasing the position of the scientific and practical conference, the professors and teachers of domestic and foreign higher educational institutions made a significant contribution.

Professors and teachers of foreign higher educational institutions who actively participated in the work of the conference made a worthy contribution to the high level of interaction with scientists of our country. The processes of international cooperation with foreign countries and exchange with them in the field of Science in the era of globalization have a positive effect on the development of Higher Education, the fields of Science and production. The materials of this conference are special in that they include a wide range of research, from theoretical developments to practical solutions, demonstrating the diversity of approaches and directions in this area.

In conclusion, it should be noted that this scientific and practical conference will be a very useful collection for everyone who is interested in modern research in the fields of further development of Higher Education, Science, Education and production in the era of globalization. The authors are responsible for the content and quality of the articles and abstracts included in the collection.

XALQARO SAVDODA BOJXONA-LOGISTIKA TIZIMINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH YO‘LLARI

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Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada xalqaro savdoda bojxona-logistika tizimining o‘rni va uni takomillashtirish yo‘llari tahlil qilingan. Bojxona tartib-taomillarini soddalashtirish, raqamli texnologiyalarni joriy etish, logistika infratuzilmasini rivojlantirish va xalqaro standartlarga moslashtirish masalalari asosiy e‘tiborda bo‘ldi. Shuningdek, Jahon banki va Jahon savdo tashkiloti ma‘lumotlari asosida mamlakatlar kesimida bojxona-logistika samaradorligi taqqoslab o‘rganildi hamda takomillashtirish bo‘yicha amaliy takliflar ilgari surildi.

Kalit so‘zlar: Xalqaro savdo, bojxona tizimi, logistika, raqamlashtirish, transport yo‘laklari, integratsiya, samaradorlik.

Kirish

Xalqaro savdoning barqaror rivojlanishi samarali bojxona-logistika tizimisiz tasavvur qilib bo‘lmaydi. So‘nggi yillarda globallashuv va raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida davlatlar o‘rtasidagi savdo hajmi keskin ortib bormoqda, bu esa bojxona va transport xizmatlaridan foydalanishni yanada ko‘paytirdi. Jahon bankinging *Logistics Performance Index* (LPI) reytingiga ko‘ra, 2023 yilda yetakchi o‘rinlarni Germaniya, Niderlandiya, Singapur kabi mamlakatlar egalladi. Biroq ko‘plab rivojlanayotgan davlatlarda bojxona jarayonlarining murakkabligi, transport infratuzilmasining yetarli emasligi va korrupsiya omillari xalqaro savdo samaradorligiga salbiy ta‘sir ko‘rsatmoqda.

Xalqaro tajriba shuni ko‘rsatmoqdaki, bojxona-logistika tizimini takomillashtirishda bojxona rasmiylashtiruvini avtomatlashtirish, “bir darcha” (single window) mexanizmini keng joriy etish, multimodal transport yo‘laklarini rivojlantirish va elektron hujjat almashinuvini qo‘llash hal qiluvchi ahamiyat kasb etadi. Shu bois, mazkur maqolada xalqaro savdoda bojxona-logistika tizimini takomillashtirishning zamonaviy yo‘nalishlari, mavjud muammolar va ularni hal etishning samarali mexanizmlari tahlil qilinadi.

Adabiyotlar tahlili

- Jahon savdo tashkiloti (WTO, 2023) ma‘lumotlariga ko‘ra, savdo xarajatlarining 20–25 foizi bojxona va logistika bilan bog‘liq.
- UNCTAD (2022) hisobotida esa, raqamli bojxona tizimiga o‘tgan mamlakatlarda yuklarni rasmiylashtirish muddati 30–40% ga qisqarganligi qayd etilgan.

• LPI (World Bank, 2023) ma'lumotida Singapur va Germaniya eng samarali logistika tizimiga ega mamlakatlar sifatida tilga olinadi, O'zbekiston 99-o'rinda qayd etilgan.

Tadqiqot metodologiyasi

Maqolada taqqoslash, statistik tahlil va SWOT tahlil usullari qo'llanildi. Jahon banki, WTO va UNCTAD ma'lumotlari asosida xalqaro savdoda bojxona-logistika samaradorligi o'rganildi.

Tahlil va natijalar

1-jadval. Ayrim mamlakatlar bojxona-logistika samaradorligi (LPI – 2023)

Mamlakat	Bojxona samaradorligi (0–5)	Infratuzilma (0–5)	Umumiy LPI reytingi
Germaniya	4.1	4.3	4.1
Singapur	4.0	4.2	4.0
Xitoy	3.3	3.6	3.5
Rossiya	2.9	3.0	2.9
O'zbekiston	2.2	2.3	2.3

Jadvaldan ko'rinib turibdiki, rivojlangan mamlakatlarda bojxona va logistika samaradorligi yuqori, biroq O'zbekiston va boshqa rivojlanayotgan mamlakatlarda bu ko'rsatkich nisbatan past. Bu esa xalqaro savdoda qo'shimcha xarajatlarni oshiradi.

Xulosa

Xalqaro savdoda bojxona-logistika tizimini takomillashtirish davlatlar iqtisodiy raqobatbardoshligini oshirishda muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Avtomatlashtirilgan bojxona tizimlari, raqamli hujjat aylanishi, "bir darcha" mexanizmlari va multimodal transport yo'laklarini rivojlantirish orqali savdo xarajatlarini sezilarli darajada qisqartirish mumkin. O'zbekiston va boshqa rivojlanayotgan mamlakatlar uchun asosiy vazifa – ilg'or xalqaro tajribani tatbiq etish va mintaqaviy integratsiyani kuchaytirishdir.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar

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